

Synthesis of Benzothiazolyl-*s*-triazine Derivatives and their Antimicrobial Activity

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Benzothiazoles¹, *s*-triazines² and 2,4-dichloro-6-triazinylthioureas³ exhibit various biological activities. The presence of thiourellene group imparts a wide variety of physiological properties to thiourea derivatives⁴. Expecting that the combined presence of thiourellene group and thiazole system in *s*-triazine nucleus may produce potential antibacterial agents, we have prepared benzothiazolyl-*s*-triazine derivatives (3a-j)

Aniline was converted to phenylthiourea, which on cyclisation gave 2-aminobenzothiazole. Cyanuric chloride and 2-aminobenzothiazole were condensed to give compound 1. It was then treated with phenylthiourea to yield the compound 2, which on subsequent condensation with various arylthioureas furnished the corresponding *s*-triazine derivatives (3a-j) (Scheme 1).

Compound 1 showed the presence of NH group in both its ir spectrum (1595 cm^{-1}) and its pmr spectrum which showed a broad signal around δ 9.85 (1H). The ir spectrum of compound 2 showed peak at 1115 cm^{-1} (thioureido CS group) and its pmr spectrum showed a singlet at δ 4.80 (2H, NHCSNH). Similarly, the absence of a peak at 740 cm^{-1} for chloro group and the presence of a peak at 1110 cm^{-1} for thioureido CS group in compound 3b, revealed that the *o*-tolyl thioureido linkage is present at position-6 of *s*-triazine because out of three chlorine atoms of *s*-triazine ring, one is replaced by 2-aminobenzothiazole (compound 1) and the second one is

Scheme 1

replaced by phenylthiourea (compound **2**). Thus compound **2** contains only one chlorine atom which should be replaced by *o*-tolylthiourea giving compound **3b**. So it may be inferred that the *o*-tolylthioureido linkage is present at position-6 of *s*-triazine side-chain. This was further confirmed by its pmr spectrum; δ 2.10 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.90 (4H, s, 2 × NHCSNH), 10.10 (1H, brs, NH of benzothiazole) and 6.85–7.45 (13H, m ArH).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 599B spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian EM 390 spectrometer. All the compounds showed satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc using acetone-ethyl acetate-petroleum ether-water (100 : 100 : 33 : 3.5) solvent system.

The various arylthioureas⁵ and 2-aminobenzothiazole⁶ were prepared according to the literature methods.

*2-(Benzothiazol-2'-ylamino)-4,6-dichloro-s-triazine (1)*⁷: A solution of 2-aminobenzothiazole (1.50 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone was added with stirring to a cooled solution (0–5°) of cyanuric chloride (1.84 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at 0–5° and neutral pH was maintained by adding aqueous NaHCO₃ solution. It was then poured onto crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol, (85%), m.p. 277°.

*2-(Benzothiazol-2'-ylamino)-4-(phenylthioureido)-6-chloro-s-triazine (2)*⁸: To a stirred solution of **1** (2.98 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone at 35°, was added a solution of phenylthiourea (1.52 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone over a period of 0.5 h. The temperature was then gradually raised to 45° during 2 h with stirring and maintaining neutral pH by adding aqueous NaHCO₃ solution. It was then

poured onto crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol (76%), m.p. 281°.

*2-(Benzothiazol-2'-ylamino)-4-(phenylthioureido)-6-(arylythioureido)-s-triazine (3a–j)*⁷. *General method*: A mixture of **2** (4.13 g, 0.01 mol) and arylthiourea (0.01 mol) in acetone was refluxed for 3 h. It was then poured onto crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol: **3a** (49%), m.p. 251°; **b** (51%), 207°; **c** (55%), 184°; **d** (52%), 179°; **e** (53%), 186°; **f** (57%), 206°; **g** (56%), 183°; **h** (59%), 144°; **i** (57%), 114°; **j** (61%), 167°.

Antibacterial activity: Compounds **3a–j** were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *P. vulgaris* and *S. paratyphi B.*, using agar diffusion technique⁹. A standard sterilised filter paper disc (5 mm dia) impregnated with the solution of compounds in acetone (1 mg ml⁻¹) was placed on an agar plate seeded with test organism. The plates were incubated for 24 h at 37° and the zones of inhibition of bacterial growth around the disc were measured.

Evaluation of antibacterial activity and comparison of the results against the standard drugs ampicillin, erythromycin, gentamycin, penicillin was chloramphenicol for *S.a.*, *B.s.*, *E.c.*, *P.v.* and *S.p.* B respectively, reveal that the compounds having chloro-substitution in *meta*- and *para*-positions in thioureidophenyl ring exhibited maximum activity.

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